

OLEKSANDR TYSOVSKYI'S PERSPECTIVE ON THE CHALLENGES OF EDUCATING UKRAINIAN YOUTH IN EASTERN GALICIA DURING THE INTERWAR PERIOD

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Abstract

The article examines the views of Ukrainian educator, public figure, and founder of the Plast movement, Oleksandr Tysovskiy, on the challenges of educating Ukrainian youth in Eastern Galicia during the interwar period. It analyzes the socio-political conditions of that time that influenced the formation of national consciousness among young people, as well as the role of the Plast organization in the development of educational ideals. The author highlights the main difficulties faced by the Ukrainian community in the field of education: political pressure, lack of educational resources, and the need for nationally oriented pedagogy. The article emphasizes the relevance of Tysovskiy's ideas in the contemporary context of youth education.

Keywords: Oleksandr Tysovskiy, education, Ukrainian youth, Eastern Galicia, interwar period, Plast, national consciousness, pedagogy.

The issue of educating Ukrainian youth in the first half of the 20th century attracted considerable attention from scholars, primarily in the context of general approaches to school-based education. However, the views of Oleksandr Tysovskiy on this subject have remained largely overlooked by researchers. Only certain aspects of his ideas have been examined within the framework of analyzing the educational system of the "Plast" organization, yet these do not provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges faced in educating Ukrainian youth in Eastern Galicia during the interwar period. This makes the study of this topic particularly relevant.

The scientific novelty of this research lies in the fact that the key educational ideas expressed by Oleksandr Tysovskiy in his academic and publicistic works have thus far remained outside the focus of scholarly attention. Drawing on archival sources such as *"Our Youth (A Psychologist's Study by a Naturalist)"*, *"A Few Words on Home Education"* (a speech from April 3, 1938), *"A Few Words on the Conditions of Upbringing,"* and *"On the Topic of Contemporary Education,"* the article analyzes his perspective on the issues of youth education in Eastern Galicia during the interwar period. Tysovskiy's ideas in the field of youth education constitute valuable academic material and require in-depth and objective study.

Despite certain contributions by researchers to the study of Oleksandr Tysovskiy's pedagogical legacy, many aspects of his creative activity remain overlooked by scholars. In particular, primary sources that reveal the essence of his contribution to youth education have not yet been sufficiently examined. This issue has been partially addressed within the context of analyzing the educational system of the scouting organization *Plast*, which Tysovskiy co-founded. The most comprehensive treatment of these issues can be found in the works of Z. Udych [8–10] and Yu. Zhdanovych [2–3], who explored *Plast's* educational methods from the perspective of pedagogical science.

The pedagogical process within *Plast's* activities was also the subject of M. Chepil's research in the article *"The Pedagogy of Plast (First Third of the 20th Century)"* [13]. M. Okarynskyi [4] focused on aspects related to the physical health development of *Plast* members and the dynamics of changes in this field. In turn, A. Okopnyi, in the work *"Innovative Use of the Physical Education System in the Pedagogical Work of O. Tysovskiy"* [5], partially revealed the pedagogical approaches that Tysovskiy employed to promote the physical development of Ukrainian youth.

The source base for this study consists of archival documents related to the activities of Oleksandr Tysovskiy, preserved in his personal archive, which is housed at the Central State Historical Archives of Ukraine in Lviv (hereinafter – CSHAL of Ukraine). Notable among these are handwritten materials, including the article *"Our Youth (A Psychologist's Study by a Naturalist)"*, the paper *"A Few Words on Home Education"* presented at a parents' meeting on April 3, 1938, as well as the articles *"A Few Words on the Conditions of Upbringing"* and *"On the Topic of Contemporary Education."* These documents are preserved in files No. 14, No. 23, and No. 89 of this archival collection.

An important source in the context of this study is Oleksandr Tysovskiy's work *"Life in Plast"* [7], which was first published in 1921 and subsequently republished multiple times. This work provides a detailed account of the educational process within *Plast*, as well as a description of the methods that a scout-educator should use to prepare youth for active participation in the organization's life.

Valuable insights into the formation of Oleksandr Tysovskiy's personality and his development as an educator and mentor are presented in a collection of memoirs compiled by his associate T. Danyliv under the title *"The Founder of Plast (On the 80th Anniversary of the Birth of Professor Dr. Oleksandr Tysovskiy)"* [1].

The issue we have raised has yet to receive sufficient academic attention, as confirmed by the analysis of historiography and source materials. This allows us to conclude that contemporary scholarly literature lacks

in-depth studies devoted to uncovering the core educational ideas of Oleksandr Tysovskiy regarding youth upbringing.

Although Oleksandr Tysovskiy dedicated a significant part of his life to scientific research in the field of biology, he always remained an educator and mentor to the younger generation. His pedagogical legacy includes not only his active involvement in *Plast*, but also his years working in school education. Tysovskiy began his teaching career in 1909 at the German girls' lyceum named after Fanny von Ditters in Lviv, where his father served as principal. After passing the state teaching examination in 1911, he took a position as a *suplent* (assistant teacher) at the Ukrainian State Academic Gymnasium in Lviv [1, p. 9]. From 1911 to 1919, with the exception of one year of military service, Tysovskiy taught at this gymnasium [11, fol. 8].

Thanks to his pedagogical activity, Oleksandr Tysovskiy was able to form his own understanding of the psychological condition of youth after the war and the changes that had occurred in their worldview. Believing that these changes were caused by a number of difficulties within the educational system that emerged in the postwar period, he sought ways to overcome them. Tysovskiy expressed his reflections in a number of works that today are of great significance as historical sources, offering insights into the key challenges of educating Ukrainian youth in Eastern Galicia during the interwar era.

One of Oleksandr Tysovskiy's major achievements lies in the fact that, despite his active scientific work in the field of natural sciences, he devoted considerable attention to the education of Ukrainian youth, dedicating many of his writings to this cause. His texts are characterized by their clarity and accessibility, free from excessive academic jargon, and often exhibit a literary quality, reflective of his talent as a writer. In his works, he analyzes the issues of youth education during the interwar period, focusing on the specific conditions of Eastern Galicia, which at that time was part of the Polish Republic.

In the article "*Our Youth (A Psychologist's Study by a Naturalist)*," the author raises the issue of the ideological gap between the younger generation and older people, paying particular attention to the topic of patriotic education of Ukrainian youth in Eastern Galicia. Of particular concern to him is, in his view, the youth's indifference to their own culture and their unwillingness to actively support and develop it through personal effort. Although the exact date of the article's creation is unknown, it was likely written in the second half of the 1930s. In the introduction, Tysovskiy clearly outlines the purpose of the article, emphasizing that his intent is not to criticize youth or those who do not share his views. This is confirmed by the author's own words: "*At the outset, I wish to dispel the prejudice... that every word (written here – author) is a stereotypical criticism of everything a student does... This prejudice is based on the suspicion that every teacher — consciously or not — demands from the student what he himself failed to live up to in his own youth*" [12, fol. 1].

The main goal of the article was not to condemn the youth, but to outline the real problems that hindered

the full development of the Ukrainian educational system both in schools and beyond during the interwar period.

The value of this source lies in the fact that the ideas it presents are expressed in accessible literary language, with elements of a stylistic, almost artistic approach, and illustrated with examples from Oleksandr Tysovskiy's personal life. It explores the psychological characteristics of adolescents in their interactions with adults — parents and teachers — who already possess life experience and aim to pass it on to the younger generation. Tysovskiy believed that the attempt of the older generation to persuade the younger was akin to two trains moving in opposite directions, which must eventually meet at a common station. He envisioned the educational process as the work of refining these tracks and directing them toward a shared goal. Unfortunately, however, Ukrainian youth — who played a crucial role in societal development — often showed no desire to seek out this common path [12, fols. 3–4].

Since Tysovskiy's main academic interest was natural science and the study of living organisms, it was only natural that youth became the focus of his attention. Working with young people in *Plast* and teaching in schools gave him the opportunity to observe adolescents over a long period — their behavior, their relationships with peers and adults, and how their worldview and interests evolved.

The author shares several interesting observations from everyday life and examples of youth self-organization during their studies. In one instance, he recalls an event that led him to a critical reflection: despite having access to opportunities for growth, Ukrainian youth often failed to show initiative and ignored their talents. While walking down the hallway of the Lviv Academic Gymnasium, Tysovskiy noticed a scrap of paper carelessly pinned to a bulletin board — it turned out to be an announcement about the library's activities. What struck him was that the author of this and similar notices elsewhere had not made the effort to make the message visually appealing or persuasive — something that might have encouraged others to visit the library. Tysovskiy saw this as a sign of apathy, a lack of willingness to work for the development of culture, and an absence of a drive for self-improvement [12, fol. 8].

In the article, the author sharply criticizes youth organizations that emerged mainly after the First World War. Although these organizations were expected to support young people and encourage their active participation in public life, in reality, they turned out to be little more than weak imitations of earlier societies. They lacked creativity and failed to develop a new cultural model that would harmoniously combine the life experience of the older generation with the fresh, modern perspectives of youth on social processes [12, fol. 11].

In our view, the criticism expressed by the author is partially biased, as it is based primarily on personal observations and does not take into account a range of external factors that significantly affected the work of scientific, educational, and cultural societies. It is important to remember that in the 1920s–1930s, Eastern

Galicia was under Polish rule, which did not support the development of the Ukrainian language and culture. This is confirmed, in particular, by a series of restrictions imposed on Ukrainian school education and the activities of cultural and educational organizations.

One especially telling example is the so-called "Grabski Borderlands Law" (*kresowy zakon Grabski*) of July 31, 1924, passed by the Polish Sejm. The law called for a reorganization of the educational system, in particular, the introduction of bilingual Polish-Ukrainian schools, in which most subjects were taught in Polish. While the official goal was to create conditions for children of different nationalities to study together, in practice, it severely limited the use of the Ukrainian language in education. The implementation of this law resulted in significant suppression of the Ukrainian population of Eastern Galicia in the linguistic and cultural sphere. As a result, the number of Ukrainian state primary schools in the region dropped sharply — from 2,426 in 1920–1921 to 745 in 1927–1928 [14, pp. 14–15], and by 1939 only 139 such schools remained [6, p. 126].

Another manifestation of the restriction of Ukrainian civil rights was the official suspension of the *Plast* organization's activities in Eastern Galicia in 1930. This was a serious blow to cultural and educational life, as *Plast* played a key role in the patriotic education of Ukrainian youth during the interwar period.

One of the key themes raised in Oleksandr Tysovskyi's article concerns the role of patriotism in the education of Ukrainian youth in Eastern Galicia during the interwar period. A significant portion of the publication is devoted to analyzing patriotic education within Ukrainian educational institutions. According to Tysovskyi, patriotism is, above all, a sense of personal dignity extended from the individual to the entire nation [12, fols. 12–13]. Tysovskyi compared true patriotism to the principle "*know thyself*" (*gnōthi seauton*, Latinized from Greek), emphasizing that it should not be rooted in hostility toward other nations. Such hostility, in his view, is a remnant of primitive instinct, which gives rise to arrogance and an inflated sense of superiority.

As an example of superficial patriotism among Ukrainian youth, he cited *Shevchenko* commemorative concerts, which he believed had lost their sense of solemnity. According to Tysovskyi, young people more often showed enthusiasm for demonstrations with anti-Russian or anti-Polish slogans than for genuinely festive cultural events [12, fols. 13–14].

Tysovskyi presented such examples not as criticism but with an educational purpose, which he specifically emphasized at the end of his article. Alongside his observations, he also offered practical advice to the youth—advice he believed should be taken seriously rather than dismissed as mere teacherly preaching.

As a prominent educator, public figure, and founder of the *Plast* scouting movement, Oleksandr Tysovskyi was acutely aware of the complexity of ed-

ucating Ukrainian youth under the conditions of interwar Eastern Galicia. His reflections demonstrate not only a deep understanding of adolescent psychology but also a sincere desire to foster dialogue between generations. He stressed that education is a two-way process, requiring effort from both adults and youth, along with patience, understanding, and a shared goal.

Tysovskyi not only identified problems but also proposed solutions, placing strong emphasis on personal example, moral values, and active civic development. His views remain relevant today, as the issues he addressed—mutual understanding, self-education, and national consciousness—continue to be of vital importance.

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